

NEW OPPORTUNITIES TO LEARN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN UZBEKISTAN

Nigina Orzikulova
Rahmonova Madina
Jorayeva Nafisa
Azizova Aisha

Department of Uzbek and Literature, Faculty of Humanities,
Chirchik State Pedagogical University Student of group 22/4

Instructor: Maktuba Makhamadaliyevna Khonsaidova

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15104468>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 7-mart 2025 yil
Ma'qullandi: 18-mart 2025 yil
Nashr qilindi: 29-mart 2025 yil

KEY WORDS

*Foreign language training,
new opportunities, government,
foreign language, school, institute,
specialist, teacher, education,
program, local staff.*

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the introduction of teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan, the processes associated with new opportunities for teaching languages, as well as the problems of training specialists in foreign languages on the basis of archival data and government decisions.

INTRODUCTION

In today's process of globalization, the effect of the radical reform of the education system of Uzbekistan is evident in all areas related to this area. The state pays special attention to the teaching and further development of foreign languages in the education system, which is a key sector of socio-economic, political and cultural life of the country, one of the vital factors that directly affect the morale of the population. at the policy level. At a video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on May 6, 2021 on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the problems in the system were analyzed in detail and priorities were identified. On this basis, the issue of attitudes to foreign language teaching is addressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 No PP-5117 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level": "... education in foreign languages It is no coincidence that the need to develop as a policy priority, radically improve the quality of education in this area, attract qualified teachers to the field and increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages "

MAIN PART

Currently, in the development of New Uzbekistan, attention is being paid to teaching and learning foreign languages. For the past five years, I have witnessed the beginning of a new stage, a new era in the teaching of foreign languages in our country. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools is required in the process of teaching foreign language classes.

In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Teaching Foreign Language, Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these

requirements, the classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques.

The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. Improving the quality of education, developing the teaching of foreign languages, improving the skills and qualifications of students in learning foreign languages has become one of the priority tasks of the state policy in the field of education. Children need to master their mother tongue and foreign languages and learn how to work on a computer.

The key to the effective teaching of foreign languages is in the process of training teachers who possess modern knowledge and have high-level foreign language skills. Foreign language is aimed at students' free and creative thinking, and in-depth training in specific directions, depending on the abilities of each student, will have a good effect. For this purpose, it is necessary to create new textbooks, introduce advanced educational standards and methods into the educational system.

It is necessary to create an electronic software platform that implements a unified supply of materials related to the teaching of foreign languages in the fields of non-philological education and specializations of higher education institutions of our country, adapting them to the fields, modern teaching methods for teaching foreign languages, and knowledge assessment. The main goal of all such issues is to create modern and innovative pedagogical technologies, educational and methodological support for teaching foreign languages in our country. Currently, the importance of learning a foreign language in personal activity and its importance to society has been instilled in the minds of young people. As a result of our young people's knowledge of the language, the opportunity to study in higher education institutions of developed countries was created. Interest in language learning developed. But according to today's calculations, although we admit that there have been some achievements, it is clear that there are many aspects that worry us all. I think that it will be effective to create conditions for students of the foreign language education course to work in educational institutions according to the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach. For this, it is recommended to introduce the principles of dual education in the organization of the educational process of graduate students, that is, the student graduating from the field of natural sciences or specific sciences will be given additional qualifications in foreign languages, and as a result, an opportunity will be created to develop a specialist who teaches biology in English.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted education, and in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing a foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. The duty and task of the present generation to the future generation is greater than that of the ancestors.

Conclusion:

Uzbekistan has a wide range of opportunities to learn a foreign language, a few years ago there was very little demand for foreign languages. In recent years, the demand for foreign languages has been increasing. Even young children can easily learn through modern tablets. Some programs are also broadcast in English and Russian on our television. Currently, teachers and educators in higher education, school and pre-school organizations are required to learn a foreign language, because it plays an important role in educating the future generation.

REFERENCES:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5117 of May 19, 2021 // [HTTPS://LEX.UZ/DOCS/5426736](https://lex.uz/docs/5426736)
2. Shavkat Mirziyoev. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Volume 1 -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" NMIU, 2017. -P.145-146.
3. I. Tukhtasinov. Teaching foreign languages opens the door to new opportunities // <https://yuz.uz/news/chet-tillarnioqitish-yangi-imkoniyatlar-eshiginiochadi-->

